

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

Milestone MS7

50% DT4H toolbox components released at the appropriate software collections

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Lead Beneficiary	UB, ATH
Author(s)	Josep Ll. Gelpí, Laia Codó, Minos Garofalakis
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Version Log

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Executive Summary

This milestone document outlines the progress made toward releasing the DataTools4Heart (DT4H) Toolbox components into the appropriate software repositories. The toolbox aims to provide a comprehensive, privacy-preserving suite of tools for federated cardiology data analysis, including data ingestion, harmonisation, machine learning, and synthetic data generation, among others. Approximately half of the planned components have been successfully developed and are now available in public or restricted repositories, depending on their maturity.

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Acronyms

NLP: natural language processing

NER: Named Entity Recognition

NEL: Named Entity Linking

FEM: Federated Execution Manager

FDN: Federated Data Node

RN: Reference Node

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1 Introduction

The DataTools4Heart (DT4H) Toolbox is a comprehensive suite of tools designed to enable federated, privacy-preserving analysis of cardiology data while ensuring compliance with strict ethical and legal standards. This toolbox addresses the challenges of securely accessing and processing distributed cardiology datasets across multiple institutions, i.e., federated data nodes (FDNs), without the need for moving sensitive patient information. The data toolbox integrates tools within a decentralised platform (see [MS6_UB_30Sep24.docx](#)), including:

- standardised data ingestion and harmonisation modules, which establish a common data model for seamless integration
- multilingual natural language processing (NLP) tools tailored to cardiology for extracting information from unstructured clinical text
- advanced federated machine learning (FL) methods to train predictive AI model and synthetic data generation models

Together, these tools form a comprehensive solution for enabling secure, scalable, and privacy-preserving federated analysis of cardiology datasets.

2 Methodology

The development of the DataTools4Heart (DT4H) Toolbox follows a well-defined methodology designed to accommodate diverse operational environments across federated nodes, while addressing the complexities of a decentralised platform (see [MS6_UB_30Sep24.docx](#)). To ensure cohesive progress, the development of toolbox components is tracked in a coordinated, phased cycle. Additionally, multiple integration strategies have been designed and adopted by toolbox developers to fit various platform requirements. This methodology ensures that all components are built with scalability, flexibility, and privacy-preserving principles, while staying in sync with the platform's evolving infrastructure.

2.1 Development lifecycle

The components of the DataTools4Heart Toolbox are under active development, with each at a different stage of the development life cycle according to the timeline of the associated task. A phase-based approach has been implemented to ensure that every component is designed, developed, integrated and tested thoroughly at the platform before being publicly released. The phases of the development cycle help prioritise core functionalities and ensure alignment with the inclusion and updates of platform components, which are being developed in parallel.

The lifecycle of each toolbox component is divided into the following phases:

Design phase

The component is in the initial planning stage, where its architecture, functionality, and requirements are being defined

Development

The component is actively being developed, with coding and implementation efforts underway to build out its core features.

Platform-ready

The component has been fully developed and tested in isolation, and is now ready for integration into the larger platform for further testing.

Testing phase

The component is in the process of testing, including functionality, security, and performance assessments, to ensure it works as expected.

Production phase

The component has passed all testing and is now fully deployed and operational, ready to be made publicly available.

Once a component reaches the *Platform-Ready* phase, its source code is made available in Git repositories, primarily hosted at <https://github.com/DataTools4Heart>. Users can easily find these components by filtering repositories with the specific topic tag (“dt4h-toolbox-component”). Some repositories are currently restricted due to early-stage development or code maturity, but they will be made publicly accessible once they reach a suitable readiness level.

2.2 Integration Models of Toolbox Components

The components of the data toolbox are designed to be integrated into the platform in various ways, depending on the type of application, execution requirements, and data access models. This flexibility allows each tool to be deployed effectively across the federated environment, either as part of data processing, analysis, or clinical data annotation tasks. Yet, they all are implemented as portable and reproducible components, distributed either as software containers or data analysis workflows properly annotated. As such, we enable compute mobility across federated nodes, reproducibility and collaboration.

Below are the seven distinct deployment modes categorised by how and where each component can be integrated into the platform.

Cogstack:

- *custom pipeline*
- *NLP app*

Integrated into the CogStack framework either as:

- *Custom-built pipelines*

Pipeline within the CogStack framework for batch data processing. This allows processing of unstructured clinical data, such as applying NLP models for text extraction, translation, annotation or harmonisation within the CogStack framework

Code Distribution	Cogstack NiFi workflow (XML)
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- *NLP tool*

NLP application in CogStack utilising libraries or services like MedCAT, to perform text annotation, entity recognition, or linking (NER/NEL) on CogStack datasets.

Code Distribution	MedCAT: web service API (Docker) containing NLP model/s
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FEM:

- ***federated task***
- ***distributed task***
- ***single-node task***

Integrated as one or more batch jobs orchestrated by the Federated Execution Manager (FEM) and dispatched to Federated Data Nodes (FDNs). Depending on the nature of the task, the integration can follow one of three models:

- *Federated task*

The toolbox component establishes a temporary shared network for collaborative model training or data processing. It consists of two parts: a central server implementing an aggregator algorithm and a client deployed on each FDN. FEM coordinates these parts to enable a synchronous Federated Learning (FL) session across the participating clients and the central aggregator.

Code Distribution	- Client Container (Docker) mounting ML model/s (Git) - Sever Container (Docker) mounting ML model/s (Git)
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- *distributed task:*

The toolbox component is distributed across multiple FDNs by FEM, with no need for aggregation of model parameters or results. Each FDN runs an independent instance of the component, ensuring decentralised and isolated task execution.

Code Distribution	Container (Docker) with the tool
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- *single-node task:*

The task is executed remotely on a designated FDN, without requiring any collaboration between nodes. This model is ideal for tasks that demand privileged access to local data but do not require distributed computing or network coordination.

Code Distribution	Container (Docker) with the tool
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Standalone: web app

- *at FDNs*
- *at RNs*

Toolbox component is deployed as a standalone web application deployed:

- *at a Reference Node (RN):*

Typically when the application requires centralised management, interaction with global resources, or publicly available user-facing web portals.

Code Distribution	Container (Docker) with the Web Application
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- *at a Federated Data Node (FDN):*
Offering node-specific services to users at the local level with direct access to local datasets.

Code Distribution	Container (Docker) with the Web Application
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Each of these deployment models ensures that DT4H components can be adapted to the diverse operational environments found across the federation, while maintaining high standards of privacy, data security, and performance.

3 Data Toolbox Components

This section presents an initial catalogue of components comprising the Data Toolbox, along with links to the corresponding source code repositories for released components. Currently, **about half of the components** have been made available for testing. Some are ready for integration into the platform (*platform-ready phase*), while others have already been deployed and are undergoing testing on the platform (*testing phase*). Although these components are fully developed and technically sound, they are expected to be extended as new data and models become available.

Table 1. Components summary of Data Toolbox.

	Category	Toolbox component	Description	Author/s	Status	Platform Integration Mean	Source Code Release
1	NLP & Translation	Dictionary lookup baseline	A baseline system for recognizing clinical terms using dictionary lookup techniques. The model is based on spacy and takes DT4H variables to annotate exact matches. It is taken as a baseline to benchmark newly developed NER+L models. Currently available in: <i>English, Spanish</i>	BSC	Testing phase	Cogstack: <i>NLP app</i>	English: https://github.com/nlp4bia-bsc/dt4h-modelanotator-api Spanish: https://github.com/nlp4bia-bsc/dt4h-modelannotation-spanish-api
2	NLP & Translation	Model annotation pipeline	The model annotation pipeline retrieves the corpus from CogStack's OpenSearch database and processes it using a model API to generate annotations. These annotations are then stored back into the OpenSearch database as JSON files for easy retrieval and further analysis.	BSC	Testing phase	Cogstack: <i>custom pipeline</i>	https://github.com/nlp4bia-bsc/dt4h-cogstack-pipelines/blob/main/OpenSearch_ingest_annotate_ES_MedCATService_to_ES.xml
3	NLP & Translation	Multilingual Machine Translation model for clinical text	Modern MT-based machine translation model to translate clinical text in every language of the consortium. The model is trained on Paraclite data.	TRANS	Development	Cogstack: <i>custom pipeline</i>	
4	FL & Fairness	FLcore	Set of FL aggregators and models. Flower compatible. Current supported models: Logistic regression, SGD Classifier, Elastic Net, Random Forest, XGBoost, Deep Learning	UB	Testing phase	FEM: <i>federated task</i>	https://gitlab.bsc.es/fl/flcore (restricted access)
5	FL & Fairness	FLcore w/ SMPC	FLcore extension including models and aggregators supporting SMPC. Current NLP tool @Cogstackeewewewnt supported models: logistic regression...	UB, ATH	Testing phase	FEM: <i>federated task</i>	https://gitlab.bsc.es/fl/flcore (restricted access)

6	FL & Fairness	FLcore w/ dropout	FLCore extension including support for centre dropout	UB	Development	FEM: federated task	https://gitlab.bsc.es/fl/flcore (restricted access)
7	FL & Fairness	FLcore w/ advanced fairness techniques	FLCore extension including support for unbiased federated learning.	UB	Integration ready	FEM: federated task	https://gitlab.bsc.es/fl/flcore (restricted access)
8	FL & Fairness	Risk score prediction for acute HF in emergency depts.	AI model for prediction of subsequent (HF/CV)-rehospitalization, cardiovascular event or mortality within 7-, 30-,90-, 180-days, 1-, 3- and 5-year follow-up.	UB	Design Phase	FEM: federated task	
9	FL & Fairness	SMART cardiovascular risk score improvement	AI model to improve the SMART cardiovascular risk score prediction. It exploits longitudinal unannotated and structured EHR data from the hospital sites of the consortium and from CardioSynth.	TRANS	Development	FEM: federated task	
10	Data Mngt.	Data ingestion pipeline to Cogstack	This pipeline takes the corpus from a specific directory, and preprocesses the data to load it at Cogstack's Opensearch vector database. The pipeline is meant to be executed in batch mode.	BSC	Testing phase	Cogstack: custom pipeline	https://github.com/nlp4bia-bsc/dt4h-cogstack-pipelines/blob/main/Raw_file_read_from_disk_ocr_custom.xml
11	Data Mngt.	Sub-dataset Materializer (onFHIR feast)	Generates a new AI-ready dataset selecting a subset of features from an existing AI-ready dataset. The tool interacts with onFHIR feast endpoints to generate the new dataset	UB, SRDC	Development	FEM: distributed task	
12	Data Mngt.	Dataset Metadata Fetcher (onFHIR feast)	Fetches metadata for AI-ready datasets to support model development. The tool interacts with onFHIR Feast endpoints, who returns the dataset metadata file with some aggregated statistics	UB	Testing phase	FEM: distributed task	https://github.com/DataTools4Heart/onFHIR_metadata_fetcher

13	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Tabular Data Generator (Centralized DP GAN Model)	Utilizes Generative Adversarial Networks with Differential Privacy techniques to generate synthetic tabular data in a centralized setting, ensuring both data privacy and utility. This model provides robust DP guarantees while maintaining high fidelity in the synthetic datasets.	LYN, ATH	Integration ready	<i>FEM: single-node task</i>	https://github.com/athenarc/SyntheticDataGenerators (restricted access)
14	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Image Generator (Centralized DP GAN Model)	Employs Generative Adversarial Networks enhanced with Differential Privacy to create synthetic images within a centralized architecture. Different versions of this model are available for various ϵ levels, providing flexible options for balancing image realism with privacy protection. Each version complies with established DP standards.	LYN, ATH	Integration ready	<i>FEM: single-node task</i>	https://github.com/athenarc/SyntheticDataGenerators (restricted access)
15	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Tabular Data Generator (Federated DP GAN Model)	This model leverages Generative Adversarial Networks integrated with Differential Privacy protocols and will be integrated with the FL core platform. It produces synthetic tabular data across decentralized nodes and offers versions with different ϵ levels to optimize both data privacy and utility. These variations provide robust privacy with DP in a decentralized setting.	LYN, ATH	Development	<i>FEM: federated task</i>	

16	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Image Generator (Federated DP GAN Model)	Implements Generative Adversarial Networks with Differential Privacy safeguards, designed to be integrated with the FL core platform. This model generates synthetic images in a decentralized framework and provides different versions based on varying ϵ levels, ensuring privacy compliance and enhancing security across multiple data sources with tailored DP guarantees.	LYN, ATH	Development	FEM: federated task	
17	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Tabular Data Generator (Centralised PrivBayes Model)	Utilizes the PrivBayes network, a privacy-preserving Bayesian network approach, for generating synthetic tabular data in a centralized system. Available in different versions for varying ϵ levels, this model ensures data anonymization while maintaining statistical relationships, with each version strictly adhering to specified DP standards.	LYN, ATH	Integration ready	FEM: single-node task	https://github.com/athenarc/SyntheticDataGenerators (restricted access)
18	Synthetic Data Generation	Synthetic Text Generator (Private LLM)	Model that takes some real data as input and generates synthetic data preventing leakage of the actual PII in the real data. Following the research survey, this model takes the approach of DP-ICL, using some real samples as examples to perform In-Context Learning several times and then aggregating the many results in a private manner, preventing the leakage of real data from the clinical sites.	TRANS	Development	Standalone: Web app @FDNs	

19	Quality Assessment	SynthEval: evaluation of synthetic structured data	SynthEval Tool is a framework which allows the user to evaluate and compare the generated synthetic data against their real counterpart. The framework includes state of the art matrix which evaluate the statistical quality and the privacy preservation of the generated data	LYN	Development	Standalone: Web app @RN	https://dt4h-synthetic-data-evaluation-framework.streamlit.app/
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